

Mapping and Translating Spaces, Cultures and Languages Experiences Connected to Empires and Missions (1500-1700)

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“Mapping and Translating Spaces, Cultures and Languages.
Experiences from the Missions connected to the Portuguese Empire (1540-1700)”

Book of Abstracts

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Wednesday, 10 July 2024 - CNR ISEM, c/o INSR

10:45 - When and How Europeans Learned Chinese

Chair: Paolo De Troia (Sapienza Università di Roma)

Federico Masini (Sapienza Università di Roma), *When, where, and why did Westerners begin to study the Chinese language?*

Otto Zwartjes (Université Paris-Cité/ HTL), *Language choices and communicative settings in a missionary context. How to learn and teach Chinese, with particular focus on 17th century Spanish missionaries and the Portuguese connection*

Emanuele Raini (Università di Napoli "L'Orientale"), *Tailoring new dresses by sewing letters: the Romanization of Chinese language as a process of cultural translation*

Federico Masini

Sapienza Università di Roma

When where and why did Westerners begin to study the Chinese language ?

It is common today to consider the study of foreign languages as an indispensable element of international exchanges, for whatever purpose, trade, diplomacy, etc. But until a few centuries ago, this was not the case. The study of foreign languages was the outcome of the century of geographical discoveries, when Europeans gradually discovered that there was more to the world than just them, the white Christians. Thus, in the 16th and 17th centuries, what we today refer to as missionary linguistics was born.

The missionaries travelled with traders, Spanish to the West and Portuguese to the East, and began to come into contact with other peoples, who spoke other languages. It was only towards the end of the 16th century that the Jesuit missionaries, mostly Italians, first realised the importance of studying the language of a people whose civilisation was at least as old as their own, the Christian civilisation. The study of the Chinese language is the effect of the cultural shock the missionaries had in discovering China and Chinese civilization.

The paper aims to present the novelty of language study at the end of the 16th century and the ways in which the first Europeans, i. e., Michele Ruggieri, Matteo Ricci and Martino Martini, began the study of the Chinese language, both oral and written, thus initiating modern sinology.

Federico Masini is a Professor of Chinese Language and Literature at Sapienza University of Rome. From 2001 to 2010 was Dean of the Faculty of Oriental Studies, from September 2006 is Director of the Confucius Institute at Sapienza; from 2010 to 2014 was Vice Rector for Academic Affairs at Sapienza University of Rome. His main research areas are Chinese lexicology, Sino-Western cultural-historical relations, and Chinese teaching as a second language. He has published Chinese language teaching books (*Il cinese per gli italiani*, 3 vols., *Parliamo cinese* 3 vols., *Comunicare in cinese* 3 vols., etc) and many publications also translated in Chinese, Japanese, and Korean, such as *Italia e Cina* (with G. Bertuccioli) and the *Formation of Modern Chinese Lexicon* (University of California, Berkeley).

Otto Zwartjes

Université Paris-Cité/ HTL

Language choices and communicative settings in a missionary context. How to learn and teach Chinese, with particular focus on 17th century Spanish missionaries and the Portuguese connection

In this presentation, I will focus on texts that are particularly aimed at communication. In traditional Latin grammars and grammars of European vernaculars, - which were designed to formulate rules and exceptions -, there was hardly any attention paid to the communicative aspect and pragmatics. The texts being discussed here demonstrate that language studies and foreign language education have undergone significant development, with a greater emphasis placed on the language user and the communicative context.

The corpus studied for this lecture is multilingual. Firstly, the possible Portuguese sources of inspiration underlying the linguistic production of Spanish Dominicans are discussed. Besides his Spanish-Chinese dictionary, the Spanish Dominican Francisco Varo is also known for a Portuguese-Chinese version. Latin and Portuguese versions of his Spanish grammar of Chinese also circulated. My particular focus is Morales's hitherto understudied *Manuale pro missionariis*. The *Manuale* is divided into books, numbered from I-IX, books I-V contain religious content, ceremonies and rites, a translation of the Kyrie, a catechism, and phrases related to liturgy (Zwartjes 2024, section 3.3), The wordlists and useful idioms for conversations are thematically arranged and include 1000 entries. This remarkable text will be compared with Monteiro's *Vera et unica praxis* and secondly, this it will be analysed from a cultural and pedagogical perspective.

Otto Zwartjes has published on medieval Hispano-Arabic poetry, the *kharjas*. He was Professor of Spanish Language and Linguistics at the University of Oslo. He founded the research group Revitalizing Older Linguistic Documentation at the University of Amsterdam. He is currently Professor of General Linguistics at the Université Paris-Cité and affiliated with the Laboratoire d'histoire des théories linguistiques. He has published extensively on Spanish and Portuguese missionary Linguistics. Published books: Melchor Oyanguren de Santa Inés. *Arte de la lengua japona (1738)*, *Tagalysmo elucidado (1742)* y "*Arte chinico*"(1742). Estudio a cargo de Otto Zwartjes. 3 Vols. (AECID, 2010), *Portuguese Missionary Grammars in Asia, Africa and Brazil, 1550-1800* (John Benjamins, 2011), Manuel Pérez, *Arte de el idioma mexicano (1713)*. *Gramática, didáctica, dialectología y traductología* (with José Antonio Flores Farfán) (Vervuert, 2018) and *Missionary Grammars and Dictionaries of Chinese. The contribution of seventeenth century Spanish Dominicans* (John Benjamins, 2024).

Emanuele Raini

Università di Napoli "L'Orientale"

Tailoring new dresses by sewing letters: the Romanization of Chinese language as a process of cultural translation

Starting from the Yuan period (13th to 14th century), and much more from the end of the Ming (17th century) onwards, Western merchants, missionaries, and individuals who travelled in China left written records in which they largely cited Chinese names and expressions in alphabetical transcriptions (Raini 2010; Masini 2019). Some of them aimed to "become" Chinese, some others only to understand the Chinese and communicate with them. We, the "foreigners", needed to interpret Chinese culture through the lenses of our original cultural categories. The first key that we used to unlock the gate of what would be then called "Sinology" (intended as the knowledge about China) was to offer a "Western" appearance to the sounds of Chinese language, in order to make them "look more familiar". In this sense, the use of the Latin alphabet for the phonetic transcription (i.e., Romanization) was a crucial tool for "translating" the Chinese world to the West (Raini 2014). The alphabet then became a powerful means to initiate metalinguistic reflection on Chinese (Masini 2019; Paternicò 2013), a fundamental device for compiling linguistic tools such as dictionaries and grammars, and finally, an element of technological innovation that revolutionized the very conception that the Chinese had of language and education (Zhong 2019). My presentation will attempt to offer a synthetic overview of the history of the Romanization of Chinese language, from the earliest attempts in the Middle Ages up to the first half of the 20th century. After a general overview, I will take the case of the Romanization of Chinese toponyms as an example to show the complexity and richness of this phenomenon of cultural translation (Raini 2022; Caboara 2022).

Emanuele Raini is Research Fellow in Chinese Language and Literature at "L'Orientale" University of Naples. He holds a Ph.D in Asian Studies at Sapienza University of Rome, where he wrote a dissertation on the history of Romanization Systems of Mandarin Chinese in the centuries XVI to XVIII. He has worked (2013-2020) as collaborator and researcher at the Center for Chinese Studies of the Urbaniana University, where he carried out research in the field of Chinese missionary linguistics, the history of missions in China and the intellectual exchanges between China and Europe. His recent publications include: "The Romanization of Chinese Toponyms" in M. Caboara (ed.), *Regnum Chinae* (Brill, 2022); *La pronuncia del cinese* (Hoepli, 2023); "Topics and Lexicon in the Western Linguistic Materials to Learn Mandarin and Cantonese in the 19th Century" with L.M. Paternicò, in *The Origin and Influence of Chinese Language Teaching in Europe* (Lamolapress, 2023).

Wednesday, 10 July 2024 - CNR ISEM, c/o INSR

14:30 - Mapping as Translation

Chair: Angelo Cattaneo (CNR ISEM)

Marco Caboara (The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology), *Mapping China for the Western World, Mapping the Western World for China in the First Iberian Globalization: three late 16th century visualizations of China, East Asia and the Transpacific mediated by Iberian agents*

Francesco Calzolaio (Society of Fellows in the Humanities, The University of Hong Kong) and Giancarlo Casale (European University Institute), *Describing China between Latin and Turkish: A Ottoman Translation of Martino Martini's Chinese Atlas*

Marco Caboara

The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology - HKUST

Mapping China for the Western world, mapping the Western World for China in the First Iberian Globalization: three late 16th century visualizations of China, East Asia and the Transpacific mediated by Iberian agents

My paper will look at three printed maps and related texts produced by a Jesuit missionary (Michele Ruggieri and his c.1590 map *Sinarum Regni*, Caboara 2022: 178-183), a Dominican friar (Juan Cobo and his 1593 *Map of the Pacific World* (Padron 2020) and a 1555 map of China which arrived in Madrid in 1575 (Caboara 2022: 49-50 and Morar 2024).

The first is a European map printed in Rome based on Chinese sources, the second a Chinese map printed in Manila based on European sources, the third a Chinese map printed in Fujian but annotated by Spanish agents in Manila.

These three objects and the printed and manuscript texts accompanying them illustrate the bidirectional flow of images and interpretations taking place between East Asia and Europe in the late 16th century.

Beside the texts immediately related to the maps, I will touch upon other translational tools such as dictionaries, reports and other archival materials.

Marco Caboara is Senior Lecturer in the History of Cartography and the History of Science at the Hong Kong University of Science and Technology (HKUST). He studied History, Linguistics and Chinese at Scuola Normale Superiore in Pisa, Beijing University, and City University of Hong Kong and received his Ph.D. from the University of Washington, Seattle with a study of the linguistic features of Classical Chinese Bamboo Manuscripts from Guodian. His main areas of interest are related to the history of cartography, history of the book, East-West interactions and Classical Chinese linguistics. His monograph *Regnum Chinae*, the first comprehensive study of European printed maps of China from 1580 to 1735, was published by Brill in 2022. He has also published on Jesuit maps of East Asia in manuscript and in print, his most recent study being "A Manuscript Map of East Asia Assembled by Jesuits in Nagasaki and Macau" Cams and Papelitzky (eds.) *Remapping the World from East Asia*, University of Hawai'i Press 2024.

Francesco Calzolaio (Society of Fellows in the Humanities, The University of Hong Kong)
Giancarlo Casale (European University Institute)

Describing China between Latin and Turkish: A Ottoman Translation of Martino Martini's *Atlas Sinensis*

These two joint papers will explore, in combination, the *Novus Atlas Sinensis* (1655), by the Jesuit Martino Martini, and a subsequent translation/adaptation of this text into Ottoman Turkish titled the *Tarih-i Çin*. The former is a landmark cultural/historical atlas of China, the first in a Western language to be based primarily on sources consulted in the original Chinese. The latter is part of a larger Imperial translation project, the *Nusretü'l-İslâm ve's-sürûr fî tahrîri Atlas Mayor*, to translate a copy of Jean Blaeu's *Atlas Maior*, which was given to the Sultan as a gift by Dutch diplomats. The Turkish translation is a composite, generally attributed to Ebu Bekir Behram ed-Dimeşqi (d.1691), but facilitated by other anonymous translators, including an un-named "Jesuit from Chios".

The presentation will be divided into two parts. First, Calzolaio and Casale will each speak about the individual authors and texts. In the second, they will present their preliminary results of a systematic comparison of the Latin and Ottoman Turkish texts--focusing specifically on the general introduction and the section describing the "Tatars", to explore the ways in which the Turkish translation was adapted to the different exigencies of an Ottoman audience.

Francesco Calzolaio is a Postdoctoral Fellow in the Society of Fellows in the Humanities at the University of Hong Kong, where he is also affiliated with the History Department. Calzolaio is a scholar of the connected histories of early modern Persianate Asia, with a focus on the connection between the Persianate sphere and East and Southeast Asia. His research explores issues of self-definition and othering, cross-cultural translation, and intellectual and scientific exchange, through a transregional lens that combines approaches of history, literature, and cultural and translation studies to highlight interregional connections and long-term commonalities. His work has appeared or is forthcoming in such journals as *Journal of Early Modern History*, *Central Asiatic Journal*, and *Iranian Studies*, and he is currently working on a book project for Edinburgh University Press.

Giancarlo Casale is Professor of Early Modern Mediterranean History at the European University Institute. He is a specialist in the history of the Ottoman Empire and its relations with the larger early modern world, as well as the history of early modern cartography, of global knowledge production, and cross-cultural diplomacy. His books include *The Ottoman Age of Exploration* (Oxford, 2011) and *Prisoner of the Infidels: The Memoir of An Ottoman Muslim in Seventeenth-Century Europe* (University of California, 2021). Since 2010, he has also served as the executive editor of *The Journal of Early Modern History*.

Wednesday, 10 July 2024 - CNR ISEM, c/o INSR

16:30 - Mapping as Translation (continued)

Chair: Marco Caboara (The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology)

Roderich Ptak (Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität, München), *Questions Related to Malay, Chinese and Portuguese Names of Selected Islands along the Sailing Corridor from Johor to Macau (15th to 17th Centuries)*

Paolo De Troia (Sapienza Università di Roma), *Overlapping of geographical descriptions in Sino-Jesuit atlases: some remarks about an analytical glossary of toponyms in Chinese missionary works in 17th century*

Davor Antonucci (Sapienza Università di Roma), *“Tartaros autem voco gentem illam...”: the diachronic evolution of a misunderstood term*

Roderich Ptak

Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität, München

Questions Related to Malay, Chinese and Portuguese Names of Selected Islands along the Sailing Corridor from Johor to Macau (15th to 17th Centuries)

In late Medieval and Early Modern times, the long sailing route from the southern tip of the Malay Peninsula via the coast of modern Vietnam and the southeastern shores of Hainan to the insular world near Macau and to Macau itself constituted the most important access route to China, and especially to the port of Guangzhou. Ships leaving Fujian for Southeast Asia also used this sailing corridor. They usually passed Central Guangdong at some distance from the mainland and then continued their voyage from North Hainan towards the Malay world.

Chinese colleagues often call this sailing corridor Xiyang hangxian 西洋航綫, or “Western Sailing Route”, to distinguish it from its eastern “counterpart” which connected Fujian via South Taiwan with the Philippines. The “Western Route” is dotted with hundreds of islands, reefs, and rocks. Maps, nautical texts, and other written sources record some of their names. Different merchant networks used different name codes to identify these locations. In other cases, toponyms circulated from one group to another group. Communication between groups and the exchange of nautical knowledge certainly involved interpreters, pilots, and captains. While we know very little about their role, it is at times possible to shed light on the history of certain toponyms. Thus, some Chinese names are directly related to Malay names, while the Portuguese used both Malay and Chinese appellations, but they also invented their own names. My presentation provides some examples for such transfers and raises questions concerning the possible background of such transfers. This mainly concerns locations inside the Seribuat Archipelago, near Hainan, and of the Wanshan qundao 萬山群島, now administered by Zhuhai 珠海.

Roderich Ptak since 1994 is Chair of Sinology, Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München, Institute of Sinology. Retired in 2021. Earlier: professor in Mainz/Germersheim and

Heidelberg, and “Heisenberg scholar”. Books and articles related to the early history of Macau and Luso-Chinese contacts, Chinese historical geography of maritime Asia, birds and beasts in traditional Chinese sources, the history of the Mazu cult, and traditional Chinese novels and plays.

Paolo De Troia

Sapienza Università di Roma

Overlapping of geographical descriptions in Sino-Jesuit atlases: some remarks about an analytical glossary of toponyms in Chinese missionary works in 17th century.

Beginning in the late 1500, with the arrival of Jesuit missionaries in China, they produced a significant number of geographical works based mainly on Western sources: maps, atlases, terrestrial globes. The main merit of the Sino-Jesuit geographical works was that, through the translations and adaptations made by the missionaries, the ideas of Ortelius, Mercator and other European geographers and cartographers were disseminated among the Chinese literati. These works do not only contain knowledge from the West, but they are also, in fact, a fantastic example of cultural overlap, sometimes showing information from Chinese sources. This process of creating and disseminating geographical knowledge has been studied consistently. However, there has never been a dictionary or glossary that collects the geographical names coined by the Jesuit missionaries, referring mainly to Western countries, used in these works, and then disseminated in the Chinese lexicon. These toponyms are sometimes difficult to identify, partly due to the lack of a specific glossary, but they are in fact a useful tool for researching this case of cultural interaction.

My presentation will describe the project of an analytical geographical dictionary of Chinese toponyms in 17th-century missionary texts. The glossary will initially be in the form of a database and will contain not only the list of toponyms found in all missionary geographical texts of the period and their identification in modern geography, but also an in-depth analysis that will provide information on the lexical process behind the name used, details on specific historical-cultural aspects of such lexical creations, in order to provide examples and shed light on the cross-cultural process of 'translation of spaces and cultures' undertaken by missionaries in East Asia since the late 1500.

Paolo De Troia is Associate Professor at Sapienza University of Rome. Ph.D. in East Asian Cultures and Civilization. His research focuses on Chinese language and literature (Contemporary Chinese media language; Ming and Qing fiction;), History of Sino-European cultural and scientific contacts, and History of Chinese Lexicon. He focused on the contacts between China and Europe through geographical material and translated the 17th century's Atlas of Giulio Aleni (published 2009), outlining western sources and his reception in the Chinese geographical world. Recently he is engaged in research on the “Treatise on Falcons” by Ludovico Buglio.

Davor Antonucci

Sapienza Università di Roma

***“Tartaros autem voco gentem illam...”*: the diachronic evolution of a misunderstood term**

The use of the term 'Tartarus' to refer to the peoples of the Central Asian steppes, and particularly to the Mongols, arose during the Middle Ages from a misunderstanding: the misidentification by Europeans of the Tatars, a fearsome and powerful tribe from Mongolia, with the Mongols who invaded Europe in the 13th century. After the sudden withdrawal of the Mongols from Europe, the term remained in use, thanks also to Marco Polo, to refer to the peoples of the Far East.

When in the early 16th century, the first Europeans, and with them the missionaries, arrived in southern China, the term was still being used without a precise idea of its real meaning. What was the knowledge and how was the anthroponym 'Tartarus' transmitted in the missionaries' sources? Which populations did they identify with this name? The paper aims to investigate how this process of (cultural) miscommunication was dealt with and finally resolved by the missionaries in China in the 17th century.

Davor Antonucci is Associate Professor at Sapienza University of Rome where he teaches History of Modern and Ancient China and History of Mongolia. His fields of research concern the history of China and Tartary in the 17th and 18th centuries, the Christian Missions in China and the relations between China, Mongolia and Europe. He has published several studies on these topics. He is the author of the critical edition of Martino Martini's *De Bello Tartarico Historia*, in Masini, F., Paternicò, L.M., Antonucci, D. (eds.), *Martino Martini S.J. Opera Omnia*, vol. V, *De Bello Tartarico Historia e altri scritti*, University of Trento, Trento 2013.

Thursday, 11 July 2024 - CNR ISEM, c/o INSR

9:30 - Jesuit Translation and Linguistic Strategies

Chair: Karen Bennett (NOVA University of Lisbon, CETAPS)

Camilla Russell (Archivum Romanum Societatis Iesu - ARSI), *Deciphering Early Modern Worlds: What Do Jesuit Sources Offer?*

Linda Zampol D'Ortia (Università Ca' Foscari di Venezia), *Translating Emotions in the Jesuit Mission of Japan: Spaces, Objects, Practices*

Martina Schrader-Kniffki (Johannes Gutenberg-Universität Mainz), *Linking sounds, writing and texts. Translation processes in the standardization of Konkani by Jesuit missionaries in Goa, India (16th-17th century)*

Camilla Russell

Archivum Romanum Societatis Iesu - ARSI

Deciphering Early Modern Worlds: What Do Jesuit Sources Offer?

This paper draws on a series of case studies from the Mediterranean, North Africa, India, and the Indonesian Archipelago to consider how Jesuits deciphered the worlds they encountered and what their abundant sources offer to scholars about the regions themselves. In particular, the paper focuses on the Jesuit presence in regions that were not subject to European imperial jurisdiction, where they operated as guests of host states and where Christianity was either non-existent or survived among a small minority of the population. The preferred Jesuit approach to working in these contexts, known as *accommodatio*—or the practice of adaptation to local cultural forms and social practices underpinned by the aim of converting populations to the Catholic faith—generated a large body of sources that provide information about the Jesuit experience. Of particular interest here, the sources also contain numerous accounts about their host societies and the interactions that took place with them. A key aim of the paper, then, is to explore these sources in terms of the opportunities (and limits) provided by Jesuit sources in deciphering early modern worlds.

Camilla Russell is Publications Editor, with IHSI, located at the Roman Jesuit Archive (Archivum Romanum Societatis Iesu - ARSI). She holds affiliations with Australian Catholic University, where she teaches at university's Rome campus, and Newcastle University (where, before moving to Rome she was Lecturer in Early Modern European History 2009-2015). She works on the cultural and religious history of Renaissance Italy and the Early Modern world and among her publications are the two monographs, *Giulia Gonzaga and the Religious Controversies of Sixteenth-Century Italy* (Brepols, 2006) and *Being a Jesuit in Renaissance Italy: Biographical Writing in the Early Global Age* (Harvard University Press, 2022).

Linda Zampol D'Ortia

Università Ca'Foscari Venezia

Translating Emotions in the Jesuit Mission of Japan: Spaces, Objects, Practices

This paper aims to analyse the strategies, and outcomes, of the translations of emotional practices implemented in sixteenth/seventeenth-century Japan by the Jesuit missionaries operating within the Portuguese *Padroado*.

Such processes of translation, enacted by both missionaries and Japanese *kirishitan* (Christians), operated in more than one direction. On the one hand, they supported the import into Japanese culture of European emotional practices, creating models of behaviour that facilitated their understanding by the Japanese. Through embodiment, these practices were appropriated, selected, debated, and expanded upon by the community, cementing them as “kirishitan.”

On the other hand, pre-existing Japanese emotional practices could be integrated into local forms of Christianity as well, following a similar manner of selection and elaboration. Printed

or manuscript Jesuit correspondence strove to contextualise, justify, and interpret them for its European readership, offering a window into the processes of rationalisation that sustained such translations.

The examples examined will focus on the translation of emotional practices linked to martyrdom and sense of space tied to devotional objects. Cases in which translation was not considered possible will be considered as well; this was generally due to the original practice contradicting one or more tenets of Christianity. One such case is the model of motherly love, which the missionaries elaborated on the example of the Virgin Mary, after refusing more common Japanese practices that included abortions and infanticides.

Finally, this paper will consider the importance that the kirishitan communities communicated emotions in a manner that was understandable to the Jesuits, over the restriction of the practices to European standards and tenets, and how the missionaries navigated the unavoidable tensions rising from the emergence of different models of being Christian.

Linda Zampol D’Ortia is Marie Skłodowska-Curie Global Fellow at Ca’ Foscari University of Venice and at the Australian Catholic University, where she is developing a project on the role of emotional practices in the early modern Jesuit missions in Asia. She has held research fellowships at Ruhr Universität Bochum (CERES – Center for Religious Studies), the National Library of Australia (Harold S. Williams Fellow for Research in Japan Studies), and Giorgio Cini Foundation in Venice (Centro Studi di Civiltà e Spiritualità Comparate). Her research interests include Christianity in Japan, early modern Catholic missions, gender history, the history of Asia-Europe contacts, materiality, emotions, and failure studies.

Martina Schrader-Kniffki

Johannes Gutenberg-Universität Mainz

Linking sounds, writing and texts. Translation processes in the standardisation of Konkani by Jesuit missionaries in Goa, India (16th/17th century).

The first grammar of one of the official languages of present-day Goa/India, Konkani, was written in 1570 by the Englishman Thomas Stephens/Tomás Estebão, a member of the Portuguese Jesuit mission, and published in 1640. The same author translated the story of the life of Jesus into Konkani in the form of the Hindu genre of the Puranas. Both the grammar and the Purana are the result of multiple translation processes in which Latin, Portuguese, English and Konkani were intertwined. Moreover, the complex relationship created by translation concerns different linguistic levels, ranging from phonemes, signs and grammatical paradigms to textual patterns. On the one hand, the talk will focus on a specific part of the grammar, the relatively extensive explanations with which the author of the grammar translates Konkani sounds and Devanagari characters, i.e. a syllabic script, into the alphabetic script, and will comment on his approach to the ‘other’ in this translation process. On the other hand, the translation from Konkani Devanagari into Latin letters forms the basis for the written translation of the story of Jesus into the textual form of a Purana. The multiple and diverse translation processes suggested here not only connect discursive spaces and

communities, but also reveal different types of translation that go beyond interlingual translation ('translation proper') and need to be characterised and defined.

Martina Schrader-Kniffki is Professor of Spanish and Portuguese Linguistics and Translation Studies at Faculty 06 of the Johannes Gutenberg University in Mainz, Germany. Her research focuses on linguistic and cultural contact and colonial translation between indigenous languages and Spanish in Mexico. She is particularly interested in translation in the field of colonial evangelisation and in the legal-notarial field; she also researches linguistic aspects of Portuguese expansion, especially in Brazil and India.

Thursday, 11 July 2024 - CNR ISEM, c/o INSR

14:30 - Jesuit Translational and Linguistic Strategies (continued)

Chair: Flavio Rurale (Università di Udine)

María Alejandra Regúnaga (Universidad de La Pampa), *Early ethno-linguistic contacts between missionaries and indigenous communities of Patagonia in Father Mascardi's 1670 letter*

Ramón Ojeda Corzo (Universidad Complutense de Madrid), *Rebuilding Ethiopia between Portuguese India and Europe: the scriptural and material strategies of the Jesuit Procurator Jerónimo Lobo*

Carlo Pelliccia (Istituto di storia dell'Europa mediterranea – CNR, Università degli Studi Internazionali di Roma), *«Losing God in Translation?» A Jesuit Sociolinguistic Debate in East and Southeast Asia (16th-17th Centuries)*

Regúnaga María Alejandra

Universidad Nacional de La Pampa

Early ethno-linguistic contacts between missionaries and indigenous communities of Patagonia in Father Mascardi's 1670 letter

Among the documents that give an account of the missionary work of the Jesuits in Patagonia, the letter of Nicolò Mascardi SJ "Carta y relacion que escribió el P. Nicolas Mascardi a los PP. Bartolome Camargo Retor de Ciloe, y Juan del Pozo y Esteban de Carboxal de lo que sucedio en la entrada que hizo a los indios Puelches y Poias siendo el dicho P. Retor de Chiloe", dated 15 October 1670, has given rise to numerous historical and ethnological analyses but has not received much attention from linguists. The linguistic data this letter provides, although scarce, are a starting point for understanding the linguistic and cultural panorama that Mascardi encountered in the Nahuel Huapi lake area.

Mascardi's letter includes a number of indigenous terms of diverse provenance: Mapuzungun language appears in the mentions of 'güecubus' (*wekufü*, harmful entity) and 'ulmenes' (*ulmen*, rich, principal man), as well as animals such as 'chine' (*chiñe* ~ *chingue* ~ *chiñque*, skunk) and 'ñaques' (*ñayki* ~ *narqui*, cat). In his account of the parliament of caciques,

Mascardi also mentions the Veliche language of the ‘northern Puelches’, the language of the ‘Poyas of Lake Nahuel Huapi’, the language of the ‘southern Poyas’ and the language of the ‘border Poyas’, which differs from the previous two in its lack of guttural sounds. The identification of some proper names (such as *Aoualla* and *Chayahau*), and terms to designate animals (*chunanes*, *xuimas*) allows a better understanding of the panorama of linguistic diversity in this Patagonian region.

María Alejandra Regúnaga holds a doctorate in Linguistics from the Universidad del Sur (Bahía Blanca, provincia de Buenos Aires, Argentina). She is Professor at the Universidad de La Pampa (Argentina) and Director of the Institute of Linguistics of the same university –from where she directs research projects on minority and minoritized languages– and Associate Researcher at the National Scientific and Technical Research Council (CONICET-Argentina) – where she conducts research on languages of the Patagonia, mainly on Yahgan, a recently extinct language of Tierra del Fuego (Argentina-Chile)– based on missionary archives and publications, exploration and travel records and other documentary sources. She coordinates with Doney Moreira Gomes (Universidade de Brasilia, Brazil) Project 9 “Linguistic Diversity in America (Amerindian Languages)” of the Association of Linguistics and Philology of Latin America (ALFAL) and, together with other linguists from Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Colombia and Mexico, she forms part of the “Interinstitutional Research and Cooperation Network on Linguistic Diversity” (RICIDIL).

Ramón Ojeda Corzo

Universidad Complutense de Madrid

Rebuilding Ethiopia between Portuguese India and Europe: the scriptural and material strategies of the Jesuit Procurator Jerónimo Lobo

The main purpose of this paper is to review the role of the Portuguese Jesuit Jerónimo Lobo (1595-1678) in the construction of a new knowledge in Europe about Ethiopia. As a member of the fourth Jesuit mission in Ethiopia, commanded by Alfonso Mendes, Jerónimo Lobo had a missionary and life experience between Africa, Portuguese India, America and Europe that was recorded in his *Itinerário*. This travel account is full of ethnographic, geographical and natural observations, which would be reprinted many times in different languages in the refutation of the European imaginary about the lands of Preste John. Nevertheless, the cultural strategies of Jerónimo Lobo as procurator and intermediary of the Jesuit mission in Ethiopia, after his expulsion in 1632, have been overshadowed in the studies that have highlighted the scriptural works of his co- religionists such as Manuel de Almeida or Baltasar Teles. In this sense, the discovery of new archive sources in Madrid, Rome, Lisbon and Paris has made possible to investigate the procuration of the Lisbon priest. From a global perspective of the cultural history of the clergy and the history of missionary knowledge, the analysis focuses on the Jesuit’s written and cartographic activity, as the author of several manuscripts and editorial supervisor; on his material culture (relics, alphabets, catechisms), as well as on the fabric of intellectuals, religious and family networks. Finally, the aim is to

present the cultural mechanisms for the transmission of African and Indian knowledges that accompanied Jerónimo Lobo's missionary propaganda of Ethiopia.

Ramón Ojeda Corzo FPU/20 pre-doctoral contract (Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities, Government of Spain). Since the academic year 2020-2021, he has been working on his PhD thesis project "Tropics in metropolitan spaces: procurators and religious agents in the cultural circulation of the Iberian world in the 17th century", Department of Early Modern History (UCM), Dir.: Federico Palomo del Barrio. Previously, he has been a CSIC fellow (JAE-Intro 2019), in the project "Diplomacy of the Spanish Monarchy: actors and intercultural negotiation (16th-18th centuries)", PI: Rubén González. Currently, he is a member of the research project "Connecting the Tropics: clerical literary practices and cultural circulation in the spaces of the Portuguese Empire in the Early Modern Period (16th -18th centuries)" (PID2020-113602GB-I00), PI: Federico Palomo, and "Virtuosa Pars" (970759), PI: Fernando Bouza. He has carried out research stays in Rome (2022, Univ. Roma Tre, PI: Paolo Broggio); Lisbon (2023, ICS, PI: Ângela Barreto Xavier) and Paris (2023, EHESS, PI: Antonella Romano). Coordinator of the Research Seminar on American History (SIHMA). His research career includes numerous communications in conferences and seminars at national and international level (Mexico, Portugal and Italy), papers' publications in peer-reviewed journals (*Hispania Sacra*, *Studia Historica*, *RCHA*) and book's chapters.

Carlo Pelliccia

Istituto di storia dell'Europa mediterranea – CNR | Università degli Studi Internazionali di Roma

«Losing God in Translation?» A Jesuit Sociolinguistic Debate in East and Southeast Asia (16th-17th Centuries)

This paper examines the translation policy characterizing the work of the Society of Jesus in both East and Southeast Asia (16th-17th centuries). Several missionaries delved into the translation of pastoral and catechetical texts and the production of linguistic handbooks to foster mutual knowledge and cultural interaction in radically different contexts.

The analysis of printed works and manuscript sources, preserved at the Archivum Romanum Societatis Iesu (ARSI), especially in the *Japonica Sinica* collection, indeed illustrates the sociolinguistic debate on the name of God, as well as the translation options and cultural strategies, among others the one known as accommodation/adaptation (*accommodatio*), and particularly during the linguistic and theological dispute issued by missionaries in Cochinchina and Tonkin.

This debate naturally also involved Rome, both because some documents (letters and reports) were addressed to the Superior General of the Order and because some manuals (dictionaries and grammars) were printed in the Eternal City, sometimes at the Propaganda Fide polyglot printing house.

Carlo Pelliccia studied at the University of Naples, “L’Orientale”. He earned a Ph.D. in “History and culture of travel and of travel literature in Modern era” at the University of Tuscia, with additional certification of Doctor Europaeus.

He is currently a research fellow at the Institute of Mediterranean Europe History of the National Research Council and an adjunct professor of Japanese language and culture at the University of International Studies of Rome.

He is also an *investigador colaborador* at the CHAM – Centre for the Humanities at the Faculty of Human and Social Sciences of the Nova University of Lisbon and the University of the Azores and a tenured teacher of foreign languages and cultures in high schools (Japanese).

His research focuses mainly on the history of linguistic, historical-missiological and socio-cultural relations between Japan and Portugal in the 16th and 17th centuries, on the Jesuit mission in Cochinchina and Tonkin, as well as on the trip to Europe of the first Japanese embassy (Tenshō shōnen shisetsu, 1582-1590). He has been publishing extensively on these topics and regularly attends in national and international conferences and seminars.

Thursday, 11 July 2024 - CNR ISEM, c/o INSR

16:30 - Translating Faith by Translating the Creed

Chair: Camilla Russell (Archivum Romanum Societatis Iesu – ARSI)

Antonio Gerace (Università di Bologna, KU Leuven), *The Apostles’ Creed Atlas: a New Digital Tool for Early Modern Historians*

Valentina Bottanelli (University of Modena e Reggio, FSCIRE, Bologna), *Across Empires of Faith: Chinese Catechisms and Religious Exchange between China, Spanish Philippines, and Dutch Batavia*

Roxana Sarion (Universidad Autònoma de Barcelona), *Matías Ruiz Blanco’s Translation of Carib Practices and Traditions in his Conversion de Piritv de indios cvmanagotos, palenqves, y otros (1690)*

Antonio Gerace

University of Bologna | KU Leuven

The Apostles’ Creed Atlas: a New Digital Tool for Early Modern Historians

Since the beginning of the 16th century, scholars tried to offer comparative and comprehensive studies of the languages with which missionaries were entering in contact, with the aim to link them to the ‘original’ one, very often identified with Hebrew (Poster 1538; Rocca 1591; Hensel 1741; Hervás 1787). In their works, these scholars furnished also translations of liturgical elements of Christian faith, which missionaries produced during the Early Modern proto-Globalisation (1500-1800) in volumes of different nature in East and West Indies’ languages, and which can be divided into three sets: 1. Linguistic works (grammars and dictionaries); 2. Catechetical works (catechisms and Christian doctrines), and 3. homiletic works. These works increased proportionally to the new discoveries. These sources were used to educate new generations of missionaries, who shall enter in contact with an increasing variety of people. The three liturgical elements which were always offered in these sources

are the Apostles' Creed (=AC), the Lord's Prayer (=LP), and the Decalogue (=D). Together with Valentina Bottanelli, I have found 16th-18th century translations of catechetical works (catechisms and Christian doctrines) in 111 languages, from all around the globe: almost all of them are digitally available. We decided to share our database with the scholarly community, through a new website which will be displayed in this presentation.

Antonio Gerace received his PhD in Religious Studies in 2017 from the KU Leuven (Belgium), where he also worked as postdoctoral researcher (2017/2018) on the development of Biblical studies in the Early Modern Low-Countries. He is (co)-author of several articles and books-chapters, and he published his first monograph "Biblical Scholarship in Leuven in the Golden Sixteenth Century" in 2019. From 2018 to 2023 he worked as researcher at the Fondazione per le Scienze Religiose "Giovanni XXIII" (Bologna, Italy), where he first focused on the education of secular clergy before the Council of Trent, writing his second monograph which is planned to be published in 2024. Now he is junior researcher 'assegnista' at the University of Bologna. He also worked on the translations of the formulas of faith (Apostles' Creed and Nicene-Constantinopolitan Creed) in the Early Modern Era. In 2020 he obtained the Italian Scientific Habilitation as Associate Professor in History of Christianity.

Valentina Bottanelli

University of Modena e Reggio | FSCIRE, Bologna

Across Empires of Faith: Chinese Catechisms and Religious Exchange between China, Spanish Philippines, and Dutch Batavia

This presentation will explore how Jesuit catechisms served as key tools in disseminating Christianity across maritime networks in Early Modern Asia, examining the impact of the Jesuits' standardised Chinese language doctrines beyond China itself. Jesuit catechism and doctrines influenced not only later Catholic missions by Dominicans, Franciscans, and Augustinians within China, but also the religious instruction of Chinese communities in Spanish Philippines and Dutch Batavia. The presentation will further investigate the reach of these catechisms, extending to the catechesis of Russian Orthodox missionaries in Northern China during the early 19th century. The presentation will further delve into the development of a standardised Chinese Christian vocabulary, tracing its evolution from initial translation efforts to the establishment of a robust theological lexicon. This analysis will be based on the text of the Apostles' Creed in five key sources, three by Catholic missionaries: Michele Ruggieri's 1584 *Tianzhu shilu*, Juan Cobo's *Doctrina Christiana* (Manila, 1593), the Jesuit Mission's *Euchologue* (1628); the Calvinist Justus Heurnius' *Compendium Doctrinae Christianae* (Batavia, 1628); and Iakinf Bichurin's orthodox revision of Brancati's *Catechism of the Angels* (1661 and 1810).

Valentina Bottanelli is a PhD candidate at FSCIRE, specialising in the liturgical texts of East Syriac Christianity in Tang China. She concurrently holds a junior researcher position at the University of Modena and Reggio Emilia, working on the project "Images of China from the Renaissance to the Enlightenment." She collaborated with the University of Sydney on the

project "Transforming the East, Jesuit Translations of the Confucian Classics," where she contributed to the integration of a database of translations. She graduated in 2021 from the University of Bologna with a thesis on the role of astronomy within the Jesuit Mission to Ming China.

Roxana Sarion

Universidad Autònoma de Barcelona (UAB)

Matías Ruiz Blanco's Translation of Carib Practices and Traditions in his *Conversion de Piritv de indios cvmanagotos, palenqves, y otros* (1690)

This contribution aims to examine the Franciscan Fray Matías Ruiz Blanco's reconceptualization of Carib practices and customs and the conveyance of the Christian faith, as theorised by him in his work *Conversion de Piritv de indios cvmanagotos, palenqves, y otros* (1690). The main aim is to analyse whether the so-called 'pacific evangelisation' project undertaken by the Franciscan missions in Píritu (today northeastern Venezuela) served, in fact, the assimilation and acculturation of the indigenous peoples under the Spanish empire, despite its seemingly conciliatory initial purpose. Consequently, this contribution enquires how Ruiz Blanco interpreted and conveyed Carib knowledge systems according to Christian structures. For this, I will first contextualize the process of evangelisation on the eastern coast of Venezuela in relation to the spiritual conquest dynamics of the Americas during the 16/17th centuries. I will then provide examples of the way in which Ruiz Blanco 'demonised' manifestations of Carib practices which he made comprehensible to his fellow missionaries by establishing associations with his Christian mentality and clerical training. Finally, I will study Ruiz Blanco's translation of the *doctrina cristiana* according to principles which were not always aligned with the orthodox guidelines imposed by the Third Council of Lima (1582–83).

Roxana Sarion holds a PhD in Spanish/Latin American Literature and Culture, UiT The Arctic University of Norway (2015-2020), where she defended his dissertation *Conversion de Píritu de Mathias Ruiz Blanco: una obra misionera en el contexto fronterizo de Venezuela (ss.XVII-XVIII)*. Since then, she has been Research fellow and Associate Lecturer at the UiT Arctic University of Norway and in January 2023 she joined the Universidad Autònoma de Barcelona as Postdoctoral Researcher Juan de la Cierva, at the Centre for Renaissance Studies. She published several contributions on the translation of Catechisms in the indigenous languages of the Nueva Granda.

Friday, 12 July 2024 - Sapienza Università di Roma - Facoltà di Lettere e Filosofia - Aula di Archeologia

9:30 - *Línguas gerais*, Pidgin, Creoles, Translations

Chair: Simone Celani (Sapienza Università di Roma)

Karen Bennett (NOVA University of Lisbon, CETAPS), *The reconceptualization of translation in the Early Modern period*

Hugo C. Cardoso (Universidade de Lisboa), *Multilingualism, stratification and convergence: the linguistic reality of the Asian-Portuguese communities*

Gian Luigi De Rosa (Università Roma Tre), *General Languages and Discursive Spaces in Colonial Brazil*

Miguel Ángel Esparza Torres, Víctor F. Acevedo López, Cristina Herranza Llácer (Universidad Rey Juan Carlos, Madrid), *From the Bibliografía de la lingüística misionera española to Interactive Maps: a Visual History*

Karen Bennett

NOVA University of Lisbon, CETAPS

The reconceptualization of translation in the Early Modern period

Between the fifteenth and the eighteenth century, a major shift took place in the way that translation was conceived. While the medieval notion of *translatio* (which referred not only to texts but also to the shifting across space and time of bodies, souls, knowledge, political power) inevitably involved change from the fifteenth century onwards, 'meaning' started to be conceptualized as transcendental and therefore separable from the sign vehicle that transported it. This gave rise to the concept of equivalence, which was manifested in different ways: in metaphors of translation that revolved around oppositions such as body/soul, matter/spirit, husk/kernel; in the bilingual dictionaries that started to be produced for use in educational and other settings, and in the transparency tropes proliferating in the new religious and scientific discourses. This paper explores the sources of this semiotic shift, suggesting that it can be traced back to the recovery of Hellenistic science in the twelfth and thirteenth centuries and the epistemological upheaval that this provoked. It then traces the development of the new semiotic through the secular and sacred spheres, ending with a brief reflection on similar developments taking place in the domain of economics as use-value was commuted into exchange-value in a rapidly globalizing economy.

Karen Bennett is Associate Professor of Translation at Nova University, Lisbon, where she coordinates the Master's programme in Translation and the Translationality strand at the research unit CETAPS (Centre for English, Translation and Anglo-Portuguese Studies). She is also general editor of the journal *Translation Matters* and member of the editorial board of the Brill series *Approaches to Translation Studies*. Her research interests include history and

theory of translation; intersemiotic translation and multimodality; and ways of construing and translating knowledge.

Hugo C. Cardoso

Universidade de Lisboa, Faculdade de Letras

Multilingualism, stratification and convergence: the linguistic reality of the Asian-Portuguese communities

The diffusion of Portuguese across parts of (mostly, coastal) Asia and the ensuing linguistic contact motivated the emergence of a string of new languages, many of which now extinct, which are commonly known as the Asian-Portuguese creoles. While the period of their initial formation is likely to be located in the 16th century, the first known records of these languages date from the turn of the 18th century, and become increasingly robust from the late 19th century. Despite the absence of primary data for the first 2 centuries or so of these languages, a comparative analysis of the later materials (including contemporary records), combined with the interpretation of some scattered metalinguistic comments, allows us to formulate hypotheses concerning the multilingual practices and linguistic dynamism of the earlier Asian-Portuguese communities. In this talk, we will show how this exercise suggests a scenario characterized by socially-stratified linguistic variation and by processes of linguistic convergence through which the coexistence of various languages led to their gradual structural approximation.

Hugo C. Cardoso is Associate Professor of Linguistics at the University of Lisbon and a researcher of the *Centro de Linguística da Universidade de Lisboa*, having earlier worked in Macau, Hong Kong, and Coimbra. He is a researcher of language contact, with a particular focus on the Portuguese-lexified creole languages of South Asia (India and Sri Lanka) and a secondary one on those of Insular Southeast Asia. His research combines a synchronic (descriptive) perspective with an interest in the history of these languages and in comparative approaches to their study.

Gian Luigi De Rosa

Università Roma Tre

General Languages and Discursive Spaces In Colonial Brazil

The aim of this paper is to reflect on the status of General Languages and Portuguese in the multilingual and plurilingual reality of colonial Brazil from the XVI to the XVIII centuries and to analyse this complexity, taking into account the transformations caused by a linguistic policy enacted by the metropolis, through decrees and royal orders, between 1722 and 1759.

We will try to delineate, within the evolutionary path of the Brazilian linguistic reality of these centuries, the concepts of multilingualism and plurilingualism in the discursive spaces in which General Languages, African languages and Portuguese coexisted and competed.

Gian Luigi De Rosa, Associate Professor of Portuguese Linguistics and Translation at Roma Tre University, is Director of the "Giulia Lanciani" Portuguese Language Study Centre and Director of the UniRomaTre Summer School of Audiovisual Translation.

Visiting Professor at the Federal Universities of Goiás (2015), Fluminense (2019), São Paulo (2022), Santa Catarina (2023) and at the University of Porto (2023), he is Principal Investigator of the International Research Group "I-FALA" and Guest Investigator, among others, of the International Research Groups "Grammar Theory and Brazilian Portuguese" and "Grammar of Portuguese", among others.

He has published over a hundred works, including *Identità culturale e protonazionalismo* (FrancoAngeli, 2011); *Tradurre l'audiovisivo dal portoghese tra variazione linguistica e problematiche traduttive* (Franco Angeli, 2012); *Entre multilingüismo y diglosia: La creación de nuevos espacios discursivos en el Brasil del siglo XVIII* (Penguin, 2018); *Características da fala acadêmica monitorada no Brasil* (L&L, 2020) and, in collaboration, *Heranças gramaticais do português brasileiro* (Cegraf UFG, 2023).

Miguel Ángel Esparza Torres and Víctor F. Acevedo López, Cristina Herranza Llácer
Universidad Rey Juan Carlos, Madrid

From the *Bibliografía de la lingüística misionera española* to Interactive Maps: A Visual History

The *Bibliografía de la lingüística misionera española* (BILME) by Esparza Torres and Niederehe (2023) collects about 1900 bibliographic records. These documents have been catalogued according to their typology, mainly grammars and dictionaries; furthermore, according to their provenance and functions. At this regard, most of them are religious works, such as catechisms, doctrines, sermonaries, confessionals, novenas and hagiographies. Starting from the documentary corpus made available by the BILME project, the project "Historia visual de la lingüística misionera española" (Visual History of Spanish Missionary Linguistics) aims to identify the languages involved, quantify and spatialize the data relating to each of them. The application used to develop the visual history was ArcGis. This approach allows us to spatialize the languages on a digital map by means of coordinates. In addition, thanks to the indexing in the database itself, it facilitates further processes of data extraction.

Miguel Ángel Esparza Torres is Professor of General Linguistics at the Universidad Rey Juan Carlos in Madrid. He has developed three main lines of research, which are often interrelated: linguistic historiography, the grammatical description of Spanish and textual linguistics, which is where most of his publications can be found. His monographs include *Las ideas lingüísticas de Antonio de Nebrija* (1995), the *Bibliografía nebrisense* (with Hans-J. Niederehe, 1999) and the *Bibliografía temática de historiografía lingüística española* (2008), as well as the last two volumes of the *Bibliografía cronológica de la lingüística, la gramática y la lexicografía del*

español (with Hans-J. Niederehe, 2012 and 2015) and *Bibliografía de la lingüística misionera española* (with Hans-J. Niederehe, 2023).

Víctor F. Acevedo López is Assistant Professor of General Linguistics at the Universidad Rey Juan Carlos in Madrid. He holds a Ph.D. from the International Doctoral School in the Humanities: Language and Culture (Universidad Rey Juan Carlos). His main research interest is the Historiography of Spanish Linguistics, with a particular focus on the History of Spanish Missionary Linguistics. As part of the team led by Professors Esparza Torres and Niederehe, he has worked on the *Historia Visual de la Lingüística Misionera Española*, which can be consulted online: <https://urjc1.maps.arcgis.com/apps/dashboards/0774f50fbc6e4c09a33487c96b16711d>.

Cristina Herranza Llácer joined the General Linguistics Department of the Universidad Rey Juan Carlos in Madrid. Since then, she has taught in various undergraduate (Early Childhood Education, Language and Literature or Advertising and Public Relations) and postgraduate (Master's Degree in Teacher Training or Master's Degree in Advanced Teaching Skills) programmes. Her main research interests are in the fields of lexicography and sociolinguistics.

12:00 - Africa

Chair: Mario Casari (Sapienza Università di Roma)

Francesco Zappa (Sapienza Università di Roma), *A parallel (and partly overlapping) contact zone: "Islamic languages" in Africa and beyond*

Moufoutaou Adjeran (Université d'Abomey-Calavi), *Portuguese Substrates in Fon, a Language of Southern Benin*

Francesco Genovesi (CLEPUL, Universidade de Lisboa), *The Lexicon of Faith: Portuguese Language and Religious Practice Inside and Outside the Lusophone Atlantic Space*

Francesco Zappa

Sapienza Università di Roma

A parallel (and partly overlapping) contact zone: "Islamic languages" in Africa and beyond

This paper aims to propose some reflections on an area of language contact parallel to (and partially overlapping with) the space on which this workshop focuses, with a view to a possible comparison. It will take as a basis the notion of "Islamic languages" introduced by Alessandro Bausani (1921-1988) in a series of articles published between the 1960s and the 1980s, in which he highlighted the dense network of shared influences that used to connect, in precolonial times, the languages spoken and written in that vast area of the globe that was under Islamic cultural hegemony. Such affinities, he argued, were the outcome of a very

peculiar, mainly bookish and top-down kind of language contact, and extended to both religious and secular domains, including literary uses. Building on Bausani's understanding of Islamic languages, I will focus on sub-Saharan West Africa, which in the early modern era witnessed a rise in the hegemony of Islam among the local political, economic and intellectual elites, relatively close to the Portuguese trading posts along the Atlantic coast. The lack of a planned, centralized missionary activity, however, makes it extremely difficult for the historian to trace back translatory practices associated to Islamic preaching and proselytizing among Muslim and non-Muslim speakers of the local vernaculars. More recent fieldwork on traditional Islamic education in the area can, however, shed some light on the role of oral explanatory practices associated to Islamic education as a vehicle for the influence of Arabic on many local languages.

Francesco Zappa is Associate Professor of Islamic Studies at Sapienza University of Rome, after serving as maître de conférences of the same discipline at Aix-Marseille Université. His research interests bridge “classical” Islamic studies, Anthropology, African Languages Studies, Oral Literature and Literacy Studies, focusing on Islam in sub-Saharan West Africa, with special attention to the uses of Bambara/Bamana as a language of Islam in Mali. He carried out fieldwork in Mali in 2000-2001, 2005, 2009-2010. He contributed articles, chapters and one supplement to edited volumes and peer-reviewed academic journals, including *Die Welt des Islams*, *Archives de Sciences Sociales des Religions*, *Eurasian Studies* and *Rivista degli Studi Orientali*. He is currently part of the research team of the PRIN project “Islamic literatures in sub-Saharan Africa: Themes, Genres, and Publics.”

Moufoutaou Adjera

Université d'Abomey-Calavi (Bénin)

Portuguese Substrates in Fon, a Language of Southern Benin

Dahomey, currently known as the Republic of Benin, received on its territory the presence of the Portuguese in the fifteenth century and the French up to the late seventeenth century (Fonsagrives, 1900 : 9). The teaching of Portuguese in Dahomey started in 1680 in Ouidah in a school run by Catholic priests who were among the first missionaries who settled down on the Dahomey coast. The teaching was delivered in Portuguese to about forty students. However, this attempt was ephemeral because these missionaries were decimated by tropical fevers so that the establishment of Portuguese was more through religion than through formal ways of education. Although Portuguese did not have a long presence in the education system from Dahomey to Benin, it has a remarkable presence through Portuguese borrowings in Fon and the related languages which are spoken in this part of the country. They show that the borrowings are mostly related to religion on the one hand, and to agriculture and nutrition on the other hand (Adjera, 2023: 170). The methodological approach, inspired by that used by UNESCO to write the General History of Africa, has mobilised several cross-referenced research techniques: spontaneous recordings, simple observations, life stories, individual semi-directive interviews and a corpus of borrowings from Fon to Portuguese. The goal is to study the hidden historical and sociolinguistic links behind these age-old linguistic practices,

which constitute the enduring memory of Portuguese colonisation since the thirteenth century for today.

Moufoutaou Adjeran is Full Professor of Sociolinguistics and Ethnolinguistics at the University of Abomey-Calavi (Benin). He specialises in language and cultural contacts, norms and variations in Africa, language policies and rights, and the Yorùbá language and literature. The most recent of his publications are:

His publications include: Adjeran, M. et Akissi, B. B. (2023). “Les langues gbè dans les premiers écrits européens. Status Quaestionis”, (25), pp. 179-200; Adjeran, M. (2023), “Romance Languages in Benin: French”, dans U. Reutner (dir.), *Manual of Romance Languages in Africa* (p.165-188). De Gruyter; Adjeran M. (2023) “Enseignement-apprentissage bilingues informels au Bénin, pertinence dans l’amélioration des résultats des écoliers du cours primaire”, dans G. Nana (dir.), *Bilingualism and its Benefits*, pp.33-53.

Francesco Genovesi

CLEPUL, University of Lisbon

The Lexicon of Faith: Portuguese Language and Religious Practice Inside and Outside the Lusophone Atlantic Space

In 1739, a group of enslaved Africans escaped from their masters and the Anglican preachers in South Carolina with one goal in mind: to join the Spanish missionaries in Florida and gain their freedom. In this new context, the fugitives could claim two elements in common with the European settlers: the rudiments of Catholicism and the Portuguese language. Thus, an event as pivotal in the formation of the United States, such as the Stono Rebellion, was marked by two unanticipated cultural components in the slaves’ fight for freedom. The paper aims to investigate how the previous two and a half centuries created the conditions for the episode, mapping the Portuguese-speaking spaces, communities and trajectories on both sides of the Atlantic Ocean. Missionaries’ letters, travel accounts, and other coeval texts reveal the existence of an intricate transcontinental network that extends beyond the dichotomy of Portuguese masters and enslaved African people: among numerous players, it involved European preachers and local prophets in Kongo, Dutch settlers in Brazil and Sephardic Jewish sugarcane planters in Barbados. The principal goal of this paper is to shed light on the initial centuries of the Atlantic dissemination of the Portuguese language in relation to religious practice, which commenced with the conversion of the Kongolese King Nzinga a Nkuwu in 1491 and persists to the present day in the lexicon of faith employed by the Afro-American Gullah Geechee community.

Francesco Genovesi, Ph.D in Romance Philology, taught in several Italian universities before moving to Sub-Saharan Africa where he spent a year in Mozambique for a Post-doc research and he taught for two years at the University of Dar es Salaam, Tanzania. He is currently a member of CLEPUL - Centro de Literaturas e Culturas Lusófonas e Europeias at the University of Lisbon. His main field of research and publication focuses on the African Literatures in

Portuguese, the impact of fifteenth-sixteenth centuries Portuguese explorations on shaping the global modernity, and on the Portuguese influence outside the Lusophone official world.

15:00 - Material Culture as Translation

Chair: Francesco Genovesi (CLEPUL, Universidade de Lisboa)

James W. Nelson Novoa (Universidad Complutense de Madrid/University of Ottawa), *Mapping and Translating India in the Papal Guardaroba (1572-1667)*

Zhongyuan (Cindy) Hu (KU Leuven), *The Delight Appeal: Pineapple's Expedition during the 17th and 18th Centuries*

Martha Lucía Pulido Correa (Universidad de Antioquia, Medellín), *A change of perspective of Colonial Brazil with Anthony Knivet's chronicles (1560-1649)*

James W. Nelson Novoa

Complutense University of Madrid | University of Ottawa

Mapping and Translating India in the Papal *Guardaroba* (1572-1667)

A careful perusal of inventories made out by the Apostolic Chamber during the *sede vacante* from the reigns of Pius V to Alexander VII reveals the constant presence of objects which are designated as 'Indian' or 'Oriental'. But just what did *Indiana* and *orientale* mean in these cases? Were they objects from the American world, the New Indies or, in fact, of Asian origin? Was the Orient alluded to the Middle, the Far East or a mental space which encompassed both? Was the idea of India static or did it evolve over time? The paper will consider as much the objects themselves as the connotations they may have had for those who encountered them when compiling the lists to try to answer some of these questions through a comparison of the different papal inventories in the chronology adopted.

James W. Nelson Novoa is currently a María Zambrano researcher at the Complutense University of Madrid. He is Associate Professor of Modern Languages and Literatures/Medieval and Renaissance Studies at the University of Ottawa (Canada). After receiving his Ph.D in Spanish Philology from the University of Valencia in Spain in 2003 he has held postdoctoral fellowships from the Fundação para Ciência e Tecnologia and the Gulbenkian Foundation of Portugal and was a researcher in the European Research Council project Diaspora in Transition-Cultural and Religious Changes in Western Sephardic Communities in the Early Modern Period, Faculty of Humanities, Hebrew University. He is the author of the book *Being the Nação in the Eternal City: Portuguese New Christian Lives in Sixteenth Century Rome* (2014), of over 30 peer-reviewed articles and of 30 book chapters. His areas of scholarly interest are Italo-Iberian cultural relations in the early modern period, the Iberian presence in Rome, early European interest in the Americas and the Portuguese New Christian diaspora in Italy in the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries.

Zhongyuan (Cindy) Hu

KU Leuven

The Delight Appeal: Pineapple's Expedition during the 17th and 18th Centuries

During the 17th and 18th centuries, pineapples, originated from Brazil, travelled to the East, carried by Europeans, and later became a symbol of China in Europe. Portugal and Dutch Republic respectively transplanted pineapples to Asia in the 17th century. While in later European works, pineapple became a cultural icon of China and Chinese people. Why did this fruit from the West Indies become an image of the East? What led to the misrepresentation? How did an American pineapple convey Europe's desire for China? Intercultural transmission of food allowed both objects and ideas to travel around the world, undergoing translation processes, linguistic adaptations, and spatial mappings across cultures. The paper examines multilingual written and visual sources, including travel accounts of diplomats, treatises of missionaries, and paintings of artists, to trace the flavorful journey of perceptions of pineapple, involving scientific exchanges, economic networks, cultural encounters, and political power relationships. It investigates dynamic knowledge circulation and how it shaped ideas about others, engaging various parts of the world in the early stage of global connection. The pineapple's association with China was not simply an imagination of Europe, nor a completely empirical learning. This paper argues that the works on pineapple served as both objects and subjects, connecting locales to the broader worlds. These works not only displayed a new place to the European readers as a carrier of what they learned outside Europe, but they also provided a space where intercultural encounters happened, which allowed people to identify the others from faraway lands.

Zhongyuan (Cindy) Hu is a PhD candidate at Sinology Department at KU Leuven in Belgium. Before she joined Sinology Department in 2021, she completed her Bachelor's degree in History and Medieval and Renaissance Studies at Simon Fraser University in Vancouver, and her Master's degree in History and Food Studies at the University of Toronto in Canada. Her research interests lie on intercultural food history and early Sino-European encounters. Her current dissertation examines how European and Chinese images of each other through the lens of food informed Sino-European encounters from the 16th to 18th centuries.

Martha Lucía Pulido Correa

Universidad de Antioquia, Medellín

A change of perspective of Colonial Brazil with Anthony Knivet's chronicles (1560-1649)

Anthony Knivet's chronicles represent an important change of perspective of Colonial Brazil. The European does not place himself in a superior hierarchy here, nor does he intend to do so; he finds himself in a situation of submission, of defense, and not of imposition. Since he left England, in 1591, with Thomas Cavendish, Anthony Knivet was already in a subordinate position. Shortly afterwards he was abandoned in Brazil where he survived for eleven years, until his return to England in 1602. There he wrote *The Admirable Adventures and Strange*

Fortunes of Master Anthony Knivet. An English Pirate in Sixteenth-Century Brazil. His chronicles show how Tupi terms are little by little integrated into the travelers' reports. For translation studies this could be of interest as we may be able to situate the precise moment in which the translating act truly takes place in Brazilian land. See: Knivet, A., *The Admirable Adventures and Strange Fortunes of Master Anthony Knivet. An English Pirate in Sixteenth-Century Brazil.* Edited by Vivien Kogut Lessa de Sá. University of Cambridge, 2015.
Idem. As incríveis aventuras e estranhos infortúnios de Anthony Knivet. Tradução de Vivien Kogut Lessa de Sá. Rio de Janeiro, Editora Zahar, 2008.

Martha Lucía Pulido Correa Since 1999, Full Professor, Translation Programme, Universidad de Antioquia, Medellín, COLOMBIA. Visiting Professor at the Posgraduate Programme on Translation Studies at Universidade Federal da Santa Catarina, Florianópolis, BRAZIL, 2014 - 2018. Ph.D. on Human and Literary Sciences, Master in Comparative Literature and Specialization in Semiotics, the three degrees from Université de Paris. B.A. in Spanish and English from Universidad Pontificia Bolivariana, Medellín. Founder of the research group on Translation Studies and of *Mutatis Mutandis*, Latin American Journal of Translation Studies, that she directed until September 2014. Besides a number of academic articles, her publications include *Filosofía e historia en la Práctica de la traducción* (2003) and the translation into Spanish of *Los Traductores en la Historia* Editorial Universidad de Antioquia (2005), Delisle y Woodsworth, (ed.).

16:45 - Roundtable on Future Projects

Chair: Angelo Cattaneo, Simone Celani

Guia Boni (Università di Napoli "L'Orientale"), Francesco Borghesi (Università di Modena e Reggio Emilia/University of Sydney), Maria Serena Felici (Università degli Studi Internazionali di Roma - UNINT), Camila Russell (Archivum Romanum Societatis Iesu – ARSI), Gaetano Sabatini (Università Roma Tre/CNR ISEM)

Guia Boni (Università di Napoli "L'Orientale") teaches Portuguese language and translation. She has translated Portuguese and Brazilian writers and poets. From a theoretical point of view, her research focuses on the study of poets who translate verses (Ungaretti/Vinicius de Moraes; Bocage/Ariosto; Jorge de Sena/Rimbaud...) or who experiences prose, as in the case of Alexandre O'Neill, who translated Curzio Malaparte *La pelle*. In 2022, she published the first complete Italian translation of Fernão Mendes Pinto's *Peregrinação* (1614), with introduction and glossary, for which she received the Premio Nazionale per la Traduzione.

Francesco Borghesi teaches at the Università d Modena e Reggio Emilia and the University of Sydney. His research addresses the diffusion of ideas in Italian and European history, especially between the thirteenth and the eighteenth century, and places itself at the

intersection of the histories of literature, religion, and philosophy. His publications include an edition of Pico della Mirandola's so-called *Oration on the Dignity of Man* (2012) and an edition of his letters (2018). Currently, he is the lead investigator of an Australian Research Council Discovery Project for the period 2021-2025 dedicated to the analysis of Jesuit translations of the Confucian canon and of a PRIN 2022 PNRR project focusing on the reception of the image of China in Europe between the sixteenth and the eighteenth century. He has held several fellowships in Europe and the USA, including the Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität, the Warburg Institute, Harvard University, and the Harvard University Center for Italian Renaissance Studies - Villa I Tatti.

Angelo Cattaneo is a researcher for CNR - National Research Council, Rome. His research focuses on the history of mapping, travel literature, and of cultural encounters, in particular on missionary practices and linguistics at the interface of European and Asian empires (1250-1700). He is the P.I. of the PRIN 2022 project "Mapping and Translating Spaces, Cultures and Languages. Experiences from the Missions connected to the Portuguese Empire (1540-1700)". His publications include *Fra Mauro's Mappa mundi and Fifteenth-Century Venice* (2011), *Tradurre il mondo. Le missioni, il portoghese e nuovi spazi di lingue connesse* (2022), and the edited volumes *Interactions between Rivals. The Christian Mission and Buddhist Sects in Japan* (2021), and *Language Dynamics in the Early Modern World* (2022). He is adjunct professor at the University of Florence and Visiting Professor at Yale University.

Simone Celani is Professor of Portuguese and Brazilian Language and Translation at the University of Rome La Sapienza and coordinator of the "António Vieira" Chair (Instituto Camões/Portugal). His main areas of research are related to linguistic historiography, translation, philology of contemporary works (in particular, Fernando Pessoa) and Lusophone Africa. He is the co-P.I. of the PRIN 2022 project "Mapping and Translating Spaces, Cultures and Languages. Experiences from the Missions connected to the Portuguese Empire (1540-1700)". He has more than a hundred publications to his credit, including *L'Africa di lingua portoghese* (2003), *Alle origini della grammaticografia portoghese* (2012), *Riscritture d'autore. La creazione letteraria nelle varianti macro-testuali* (2016), *O espólio Pessoa* (2020), *Lingue romanze in Africa* (2021) and *Culture di lingua portoghese* (2023).

Maria Serena Felici (Università degli Studi Internazionali di Roma - UNINT) is Professor of Portuguese Language and Translation. She has a PhD from the Università Roma Tre with a thesis on *Eça de Queirós* and is the author of several essays on the Portuguese language and Lusophone literatures, including *Alla periferia del progresso. Le correnti politiche ottocentesche in Eça de Queirós e Leopoldo Alas*. She translates Portuguese and Brazilian authors, such as Machado de Assis. In 2023 she was a Visiting Professor at the Universidade

Federal do Paraná (UFPR). She currently coordinates the UNINT research project “Languages and knowledge moving through time. Metalinguistic manuscript tools produced within the scope of the Portuguese patronage between the sixteenth and eighteenth centuries”.

Camilla Russell is Publications Editor, with IHSI, located at the Roman Jesuit Archive (Archivum Romanum Societatis Iesu – ARSI). She holds affiliations with Australian Catholic University, where she teaches at University’s Rome Campus, and Newcastle University (where, before moving to Rome she was Lecturer in Early Modern European History 2009-2015). She works on the cultural and religious history of Renaissance Italy and the Early Modern world and among her publications are the two monographs, *Giulia Gonzaga and the Religious Controversies of Sixteenth-Century Italy* (Brepols, 2006) and *Being a Jesuit in Renaissance Italy: Biographical Writing in the Early Global Age* (Harvard University Press, 2022).

Gaetano Sabatini is Professor of Economic History at the University of Roma Tre. From 2020 to 2024 he was Director of ISEM - Institute of Mediterranean European History - CNR. He has carried out research and teachings in scientific institutions in France, Great Britain, Portugal, Spain, the United States, Mexico, Argentina, Brazil and India. He is an expert in the history of economic development, with reference to the history of public finance, private credit and trade networks in the Mediterranean, the Iberian Peninsula and Latin America. He authored and edited more than 240 publications, including *Polycentric Monarchies: How Did Early Modern Spain and Portugal Achieve and Maintain a Global Hegemony?* (2012), *Dalla colonizzazione agraria alle nuove migrazioni* (2020); *Paper and the economy of knowledge in the Early Modern Mediterranean. Finance, semiotics, and the communication revolution* (2023).

PROGRAMME AND CALL FOR PAPERS

Mapping and Translating Spaces, Cultures and Languages Experiences Connected to Empires and Missions (1500-1700)

INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE

Rome, 10-12 July 2024

Istituto di Storia dell'Europa Mediterranea, Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche

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Dipartimento di Studi Europei, Americani e Interculturali, Sapienza Università di Roma

Progetti di Ricerca di Rilevante Interesse Nazionale (PRIN 2022) - Ref.: 20222SY2K7

“Mapping and Translating Spaces, Cultures and Languages.
Experiences from the Missions connected to the Portuguese Empire (1540-1700)”

PROGRAMME

Wednesday, 10 July 2024 - CNR ISEM, c/o INSR

9:30 Welcome coffee

10:00 - Greetings and Introduction

Gaetano Platania (Istituto Nazionale di Studi Romani), Gaetano Sabatini (Università Roma Tre, CNR ISEM)

Angelo Cattaneo (CNR ISEM), Simone Celani (Sapienza Università di Roma), *Introduction*

10:45 - When and How Europeans Learned Chinese

Chair: Paolo De Troia (Sapienza Università di Roma)

Federico Masini (Sapienza Università di Roma), *When, where, and why did Westerners begin to study the Chinese language?*

Otto Zwartjes (Université Paris-Cité/ HTL), *Language choices and communicative settings in a missionary context. How to learn and teach Chinese, with particular focus on 17th century Spanish missionaries and the Portuguese connection*

Emanuele Raini (Università di Napoli "L'Orientale"), *Tailoring new dresses by sewing letters: the Romanization of Chinese language as a process of cultural translation*

13:00 Lunch break

14:30 - Mapping as Translation

Chair: Angelo Cattaneo (CNR ISEM)

Marco Caboara (The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology), *Mapping China for the Western World, Mapping the Western World for China in the First Iberian Globalization: three late 16th century visualizations of China, East Asia and the Transpacific mediated by Iberian agents*

Francesco Calzolaio (Society of Fellows in the Humanities, The University of Hong Kong) and Giancarlo Casale (European University Institute), *Describing China between Latin and Turkish: A Ottoman Translation of Martino Martini's Chinese Atlas*

16:00 Coffee break

16:30 - Mapping as Translation (continued)

Chair: Marco Caboara (The Hong Kong University of Science and Technology)

Roderich Ptak (Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität, München), *Questions Related to Malay, Chinese and Portuguese Names of Selected Islands along the Sailing Corridor from Johor to Macau (15th to 17th Centuries)*

Paolo De Troia (Sapienza Università di Roma), *Overlapping of geographical descriptions in Sino-Jesuit atlases: some remarks about an analytical glossary of toponyms in Chinese missionary works in 17th century*

Davor Antonucci (Sapienza Università di Roma), *"Tartaros autem voco gentem illam...": the diachronic evolution of a misunderstood term*

Thursday, 11 July 2024 - CNR ISEM, c/o INSR

9:30 - Jesuit Translational and Linguistic Strategies

Chair: Karen Bennett (NOVA University of Lisbon, CETAPS)

Camilla Russell (Archivum Romanun Societatis Iesu – ARSI), *Deciphering Early Modern Worlds: What Do Jesuit Sources Offer?*

Linda Zampol D'Ortia (Università Ca' Foscari di Venezia), *Translating Emotions in the Jesuit Mission of Japan: Spaces, Objects, Practices*

Martina Schrader-Kniffki (Johannes Gutenberg-Universität Mainz), *Linking sounds, writing and texts. Translation processes in the standardization of Konkani by Jesuit missionaries in Goa, India (16th-17th century)*

11:00 Coffee break

11:30 - Roundtable: Missionary Archives and Linguistic-Cultural Interactions

Chairs: Angelo Cattaneo, Simone Celani, Camilla Russell

Participants: Mario Alfarano, O.Carm., e Simona Serci (Archivio Generale Ordine Carmelitano); Flavio Belluomini (Archivio Storico 'de Propaganda Fide'); Angelo Lanfranchi, OCD, e Axel Alt (Archivio Generale, Ordine dei Carmelitani Scalzi); Festo Mkenda, S.J. (Archivum Romanun Societatis Iesu – ARSI); Patrizia Morelli (Archivio Ordine Frati Minori Cappuccini); Andrés Gómez Roza, O.S.A (Ordine di Sant'Agostino)

Discussants: Francesco Borghesi (Università di Modena e Reggio Emilia/University of Sydney), Massimo Carlo Giannini (Università di Teramo/Universidad Complutense, Madrid)

13:30 - Lunch break

14:30 - Jesuit Translational and Linguistic Strategies (continued)

Chair: Flavio Rurale (Università di Udine)

María Alejandra Regúnaga (Universidad de La Pampa), *Early ethno-linguistic contacts between missionaries and indigenous communities of Patagonia in Father Mascardi's 1670 letter*

Ramón Ojeda Corzo (Universidad Complutense de Madrid), *Rebuilding Ethiopia between Portuguese India and Europe: the scriptural and material strategies of the Jesuit Procurator Jerónimo Lobo*

Carlo Pelliccia (Istituto di storia dell'Europa mediterranea-CNR, Università degli Studi Internazionali di Roma), *«Losing God in Translation?» A Jesuit Sociolinguistic Debate in East and Southeast Asia (16th-17th Centuries)*

16:00 - Coffee break

16:30 - Translating Faith by Translating the Creed

Chair: Camilla Russell (Archivum Romanun Societatis Iesu – ARSI)

Antonio Gerace (Università di Bologna/KU Leuven), *The Apostles' Creed Atlas: a New Digital Tool for Early Modern Historians*

Valentina Bottanelli (University of Modena e Reggio, FSCIRE, Bologna), *Across Empires of Faith: Chinese Catechisms and Religious Exchange between China, Spanish Philippines, and Dutch Batavia*

Roxana Sarion (Universidad Autònoma de Barcelona), *Matías Ruiz Blanco's Translation of Carib Practices and Traditions in his Conversion de Piritv de indios cvmanagotos, palenqves, y otros (1690)*

20:30 - Social Dinner for Presenters, Chairs and Discussants

Friday, 12 July 2024 - Sapienza Università di Roma - Facoltà di Lettere e Filosofia - Aula di Archeologia

9:30 - Línguas gerais, Pidgin, Creoles, Translations

Chair: Simone Celani (Sapienza Università di Roma)

Karen Bennett (NOVA University of Lisbon, CETAPS), *The reconceptualization of translation in the Early Modern period*

Hugo C. Cardoso (Universidade de Lisboa), *Multilingualism, stratification and convergence: the linguistic reality of the Asian-Portuguese communities*

Gian Luigi De Rosa (Università Roma Tre), *General Languages and Discursive Spaces in Colonial Brazil*

Miguel Ángel Esparza Torres, Víctor F. Acevedo López, Cristina Herranza Llácer (Universidad Rey Juan Carlos, Madrid), *From the Bibliografía de la lingüística misionera española to Interactive Maps: A Visual History*

11:30 - Coffee break

12:00 - Africa

Chair: Mario Casari (Sapienza Università di Roma)

Francesco Zappa (Sapienza Università di Roma), *A parallel (and partly overlapping) contact zone: "Islamic languages" in Africa and beyond*

Moufoutaou Adjeran (Université d'Abomey-Calavi), *Portuguese Substrates in Fon, a Language of Southern Benin*

Francesco Genovesi (CLEPUL, Universidade de Lisboa), *The Lexicon of Faith: Portuguese Language and Religious Practice Inside and Outside the Lusophone Atlantic Space*

13:30 - Lunch break

15:00 - Material Culture as Translation

Chair: Francesco Genovesi (CLEPUL, Universidade de Lisboa)

James W. Nelson Novoa (Universidad Complutense de Madrid/University of Ottawa), *Mapping and Translating India in the Papal Guardaroba (1572-1667)*

Zhongyuan (Cindy) Hu (KU Leuven), *The Delight Appeal: Pineapple's Expedition during the 17th and 18th Centuries*

Martha Lucía Pulido Correa (Universidad de Antioquia, Medellín), *A change of perspective of Colonial Brazil with Anthony Knivet's chronicles (1560-1649)*

16:45 - Roundtable on Future Projects

Chair: Angelo Cattaneo, Simone Celani

Guia Boni (Università di Napoli "L'Orientale"), Francesco Borghesi (Università di Modena e Reggio Emilia/University of Sydney), Maria Serena Felici (Università degli Studi Internazionali di Roma - UNINT), Camila Russell (Archivum Romanun Societatis Iesu – ARSI), Gaetano Sabatini (Università Roma Tre/CNR ISEM)

17:45 - Final Remarks

18:00 - Farewell Drink

CALL FOR PAPERS

Mapping and Translating Spaces, Cultures and Languages Experiences Connected to Empires and Missions (1500-1700)

Rome, 10-12 July 2024

This exploratory workshop has its roots in the PRIN 2022 (Projects of Relevant National Interest) "Mapping and Translating Spaces, Cultures and Languages: Experiences from the Missions connected to the Portuguese Empire (1540-1700)" (MAT), selected by the Ministry of University and Research (MUR, Italian Republic) and funded by the European Union (NextGenerationEU). This project combines the methods of history with those of linguistics and translation studies to advance an interdisciplinary analysis of the processes of cultural (mis)communication and (mis)translation among communities across the Portuguese Empire and *Padroado* (Royal Patronage) between 1540 and 1700.

MAT develops two closely related research *foci*: 1. Collecting, cataloguing and making available in open access the largest possible documentation of forgotten primary sources that attest to the first cultural and linguistic contacts between European languages and Amerindian, African and Asian languages, in particular, but non exclusively, in the spaces of the missions connected to the Portuguese Empire; and 2. Developing a comparative analysis of Sub-Saharan Africa and China from c. 1500 to c. 1700, as two paradigmatic case studies with respect to linguistic and cultural interactions, involving missionaries, local communities, merchants, imperial agents and travellers.

For more complete information about the MAT project see:

<https://sites.google.com/uniroma1.it/mapping-translating-prin22-cnr/>

The goal of this first exploratory workshop is to place these two *foci* in the broader possible transdisciplinary research perspectives to compare, contextualize, connect, and conceptualize them in both diachronic and synchronic cultural contexts, within the other areas encompassed or connected to the Portuguese Empire (such as Brasil, India, Tonkin and Cochinchina, the Spice Islands, and Japan), and bordering it, such as Islamic Africa, Ethiopia, Persia, the Mughal Empire, Islamic Southeast Asia, and the territories encompassed by the Spanish Empire, in the period 1500-1700.

We especially welcome papers or panels dealing with (but not limited to):

- Bilingual / trilingual / multilingual and metalinguistic works, analysed from cultural and connected history perspectives;
- Travel reports, letters and maps that result from or speak of multilingual and translational practices in non-European contexts;

- Linguistic and translational practices in religious proselytism and sharing (e.g. Christianity, Islam and Buddhism) from a comparative perspective;
- Agents and institutions of cultural and linguistic translation and their strategies, tools, and goals;
- Multilingual practices (trade, translation, teaching) within multilingual communities and societies;
- Exchange and/or transfer of scientific and technological knowledge as forms of linguistic and translational practices;
- Visual arts and the representation of linguistic and translational practices.

Proposals

We welcome proposals of individual papers and/or panels. Each paper will be allocated 25 minutes, in sessions with a total time length of one and a half hours. Please send abstracts (up to 250 words) together with a short CV (up to 200 words) for individual papers in one file. Panel proposals should also include an abstract of the panel's theme (up to 250 words) as well as abstracts of each paper, and CVs of the organizer/s and each panellist, all in one file.

Abstracts and CVs should be sent to: 2024.mapping.translating@gmail.com by **March 31, 2024**.

The official language of the conference will be English, and all presentations must be in that language.

A selection of papers could be considered for publication, either in a special issue of a scientific journal or in a volume edited by the organizers, in English, after a peer-review process.

Practical details

The conference will be held on July 10-12, 2024 in the Department of European, American and Intercultural Studies at Sapienza University of Rome and ISEM - Institute of European Mediterranean History of the CNR - National Research Council of Italy and hosted by the Project "Mapping and Translating Spaces, Cultures and Languages: Experiences from the Missions connected to the Portuguese Empire (1540-1700)". There are no registration fees.

ADDRESSES, LOGISTICS AND PRACTICAL DETAILS

The conference will be held in Rome on 10 and 11 July 2024 at ISEM - Institute of European Mediterranean History of the CNR - National Research Council of Italy (c/o Istituto Nazionale di Studi Romani) and on 12 July 2024 in the Department of European, American and Intercultural Studies at Sapienza University of Rome, Faculty of Letters.

The Book of Abstracts and the Programme are available online at:

<https://sites.google.com/uniroma1.it/mapping-translating-prin22-cnr/workshop-2024?authuser=0>

The conference is conceived, organised and hosted by the **PRIN 2022 Project “Mapping and Translating Spaces, Cultures and Languages: Experiences from the Missions connected to the Portuguese Empire (1540-1700)”** - ref. 20222SY2K7:

<https://sites.google.com/uniroma1.it/mapping-translating-prin22-cnr/home>

There are no registration and participation fees. The official language of the conference is English.

10 and 11 July 2024

CNR - Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche
ISEM - Istituto di Storia dell'Europa Mediterranea
c/o Istituto Nazionale di Studi Romani
Piazza Cavalieri di Malta, 2
00153 Rome

12 July 2024

Sapienza Università di Roma
Facoltà di Lettere e Filosofia
Aula di Archeologia
P.le Aldo Moro, 5
00185 Rome

For enquiries, please contact Angelo Cattaneo and Simone Celani at:

2024.mapping.translating@gmail.com

Mapping and Translating Spaces, Cultures and Languages Experiences Connected to Empires and Missions (1500-1700)

Concept and scientific organisation

Angelo Cattaneo, Simone Celani

Scientific Committee

Angelo Cattaneo, Simone Celani, Beatrice Akissi Boutin, Paolo de Troia, Massimo Carlo Giannini, Flavio Rurale, Camilla Russell, Gaetano Sabatini

Organising Committee

Angelo Cattaneo, Simone Celani, Paolo De Troia, Maurizio Gentilini, Michela Graziosi, Giulia Maggiore, Carlo Pelliccia

Data Media Management

Francesca Di Donato, Lottie Provost

The *Book of Abstracts and Programme* is available online at:

<https://sites.google.com/uniroma1.it/mapping-translating-prin22-cnr/workshop-2024?authuser=0>

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Progetti di Ricerca di Rilevante Interesse Nazionale (PRIN 2022)

“Mapping and Translating Spaces, Cultures and Languages. Experiences from the Missions connected to the Portuguese Empire (1540-1700)”

Ref.: 20222SY2K7 - CUP: B53D23001120006

in collaboration with

Istituto Nazionale di Studi Romani

Cattedra "António Vieira"
(Istituto Camões/Portugal)

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